

Data Structures and Algorithms

Recursion: Divide and Conquer Algorithms

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Data Structures & Algorithms: a General Look

DATA STRUCTURES

Lecture #2

ALGORITHMS

Lecture #6

**This lecture !!
Lecture #7**

Complexity Analysis

Lecture #3

Lecture #4

Quick Review with Kahoot Questions

Divide and Conquer Algorithms

Created 23 minutes ago • 3 plays

Visible to everyone

3 Questions

Play **Challenge**

The image shows a Kahoot! quiz interface. On the left, there is a diagram illustrating the divide and conquer process. It consists of three levels of nodes: a top blue oval labeled 'Problem', a middle white oval labeled 'Subproblem', and two bottom white ovals labeled 'Compute Subproblem'. Red arrows point from 'Problem' to 'Subproblem', and from 'Subproblem' to the two 'Compute Subproblem' nodes. Blue arrows point from the two 'Compute Subproblem' nodes back to 'Subproblem', and from 'Subproblem' back to 'Problem'. The text 'split / merge' is written in red between the 'Problem' and 'Subproblem' nodes, and in blue between the 'Subproblem' and 'Compute Subproblem' nodes. A grey checkmark icon is in the top left corner. In the top right corner, there is a star icon and a vertical ellipsis. Below the title, it says 'Created 23 minutes ago • 3 plays'. Below that, there is a lock icon and the text 'Visible to everyone'. In the center, there is a grey oval with the text '3 Questions'. At the bottom right, there are two green buttons: 'Play' and 'Challenge'.

Divide and Conquer Algorithms

- An efficient divide and conquer algorithm consists of the following parts:
 - **Divide** the problem into a number of subproblems that are smaller instances of the same problem.
 - **Conquer** the subproblems by solving them recursively.
 - If they are small enough, solve the subproblems as "base cases".
 - *Combine* the solutions to the subproblems into the solution for the original problem.

A "divide and conquer algorithm" contains at least two recursive calls.

Divide and Conquer Algorithms

If a "Divide and Conquer Algorithm" that divides the problem into 2 subproblems, expands out two more recursive steps for a given input, we get the following:

Because divide-and-conquer creates at least two subproblems, a divide-and-conquer algorithm makes multiple recursive calls.

Divide and Conquer Algorithms

1. Divide the problem into a number of subproblems that are smaller instances of the same problem.

Divide and Conquer Algorithms

2. Conquer the subproblems by solving them recursively.

2.1. If subproblems are small enough, solve the subproblems as **"base cases"**.

Divide and Conquer Algorithms

2. Conquer the subproblems by solving them recursively.

2.1. If subproblems are small enough, solve the subproblems as "base cases".

2.2. *Combine* the solutions to the subproblems into the solution for the original problem.

Kahoot Question #1

Answer the following question:

Skip

112

Which of the following statements is TRUE regarding "Divide and Conquer Algorithms"?

Answer: Divide and conquer algorithms have at least two recursive calls

Any recursive algorithm is a divide and conquer algorithm.

Divide & conquer algorithms have at least 2 recursive calls

Divide & conquer algorithms have exactly 2 recursive calls

Divide & conquer algorithms have only 1 recursive call

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

Definition: Given (possibly negative) integers A_1, A_2, \dots, A_N , find (and identify the sequence corresponding to) the maximum value of $\sum_{k=i}^j A_k$. The maximum contiguous subsequence sum is zero if all integers are negative.

Maximum sum subarray problem

- find the contiguous subarray who has the maximum sum

**Remember
"Lecture#4:
Complexity
Analysis"**

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

Brute Force Algorithm (i. e., $O(N^3)$ Algorithm)

```
public static int maxContiguousSum(int [] array){
    int maxSum = 0;
    for(int i = 0; i < array.length; i++) {
        for(int j = i; j < array.length; j++) {
            int thisSum = 0;
            for (int k = i; k <= j; k++)
                thisSum += array[k];
            if(thisSum > maxSum)
                maxSum = thisSum; }
        }
    return maxSum;
}
```

Lecture#4

Improved Algorithm (i. e., $O(N^2)$ Algorithm)

- Let's use the fact that $\sum_{k=i}^j A_k = A_j + \sum_{k=i}^{j-1} A_k$

```
public static int maxContiguousSum(int [] array){
    int maxSum = 0;
    for(int i = 0; i < array.length; i++) {
        int thisSum = 0;
        for(int j = i; j < array.length; j++)
        {
            thisSum += array[j];
            if(thisSum > maxSum)
                maxSum = thisSum; }
        }
    return maxSum;
}
```

Lecture#4

This Lecture (i.e., Lecture#7), we'll present a "divide and conquer algorithm" to solve maximum contiguous subarray sum problem

Linear Algorithm (i. e., $O(N)$ Algorithm)

```
public static int maxContiguousSum(int [] array){
    int maxSum = 0;
    int prev = array[0];
    for(int i = 1; i < array.length; i++) {
        if(prev <= 0)
            prev = array[i];
        else
            prev += array[i];
        maxSum = Math.max(prev, maxSum); }
    return maxSum;
}
```

Lecture#4

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

The maximum contiguous sum can occur in one of 3 ways.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

Case 3: It begins in the first half and ends in the second half.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

First, let's **focus on Case 3**. Try to find out how we could calculate sums of items in a subarray that start in the first half and end in the second half.

Case 3: It begins in the first half and ends in the second half.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

Right to left scan:
start from the
border between the
two halves

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

Left to right scan:
start from the
border between the
two halves

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Suppose that the sample input to our divide and conquer algorithm is $\{4, -3, 5, -2, -1, 2, 6, -2\}$

Summing maximum sum for the first half and maximum sum for the second half gives:

$$4 + 7 = 11$$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- A divide and conquer algorithm to solve the maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem:
 1. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the first half.
 2. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the second half.
 3. Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that begins in the first half and ends at the second half.
 4. Choose the largest of three sums.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Base case

Lines #9 and #10 are equivalent to:

```
if(left == right) {
    if(a[left] > 0)
        return a[left];
    else
        return 0;
}
```

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- A divide and conquer algorithm to solve the maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem:
 1. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the first half.
 2. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the second half.
 3. Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that begins in the first half and ends at the second half.
 4. Choose the largest of three sums.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the **first half**.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- A divide and conquer algorithm to solve the maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem:
 1. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the first half.
 2. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the second half.
 3. Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that begins in the first half and ends at the second half.
 4. Choose the largest of three sums.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the **second half**.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- A divide and conquer algorithm to solve the maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem:
 1. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the first half.
 2. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the second half.
 3. Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that begins in the first half and ends at the second half.
 4. Choose the largest of three sums.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that begins in the first half and ends at the second half.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum in the first half starting at border between two halves ending at the first item.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum in the second half, starting from the border between the two halves and that ending at the last item.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- A divide and conquer algorithm to solve the maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem:
 1. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the first half.
 2. Recursively compute the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that resides entirely in the second half.
 3. Compute, the maximum contiguous subsequence sum that begins in the first half and ends at the second half.
 4. Choose the largest of three sums.

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Choose the largest of three sums.

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Let $T(N)$ represent the function to estimate time to solve a maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem of size N .

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Base case

For $N = 1$, it takes constant time to execute lines 9 and 10. Hence $T(1) = 1$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

For $N > 1$, the program must perform 2 recursive calls and also compute maximum sum for **case 3** (i.e., maximum contiguous subsequence sum starts in the first half and ends in the second half)

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Execution time of the *recursive call for first half of the sequence* will be $T(N/2)$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Execution time of the *recursive call for second half of the sequence* will be **$T(N/2)$**

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12     int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13     int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15     for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16         leftBorderSum += a[i];
17         if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18             maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19     }
20
21     for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22         rightBorderSum += a[i];
23         if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24             maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25     }
26
27     return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Execution time of the *recursive calls for first and halves of the sequence* will be **$2 * T(N/2)$**

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12     int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13     int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15     for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16         leftBorderSum += a[i];
17         if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18             maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19     }
20
21     for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22         rightBorderSum += a[i];
23         if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24             maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25     }
26
27     return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Execution time of the *recursive calls for first and second halves of the sequence* will be **$2 * T(N/2)$**

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Execution time for computing maximum sum for **case 3** (i.e., maximum contiguous subsequence sum starts in the first half and ends in the second half) will be $O(N)$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

```
4 public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

Hence, execution time for the program can be expressed as follows:

$$T(1) = 1 \text{ for } N = 1$$

$$T(N) = 2T\left(\frac{N}{2}\right) + O(N) \text{ for } N > 1$$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

Theorem: Assuming that N is a power of 2, the solution to the equation $T(N) = 2T(N/2) + N$, with initial condition $T(1) = 1$, is $T(N) = N \log N + N$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

$$T(N) = 2 * T(N/2) + N \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$T(N/2) = 2 * T(N/4) + N/2 \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Substitute Equation 2 into Equation 1 gives:

$$T(N) = 2^2 * T(N/2^2) + 2 * N \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

$$T(N/4) = 2 * T(N/8) + N/4 \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

Substitute Equation 4 into Equation 3 gives:

$$T(N) = 2^3 * T\left(\frac{N}{2^3}\right) + 3 * N \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

$$T(N) = 2 * T(N/2) + N \quad \text{for } i = 1$$

$$T(N) = 2^2 * T(N/2^2) + 2 * N \quad \text{for } i = 2$$

$$T(N) = 2^3 * T(N/2^3) + 3 * N \quad \text{for } i = 3$$

·
·
·

$$T(N) = 2^k * T(N/2^k) + k * N \quad \text{for } i = k$$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

$$T(N) = 2 * T(N/2) + N \quad \text{for } i = 1$$

$$T(N) = 2^2 * T(N/2^2) + 2 * N \quad \text{for } i = 2$$

$$T(N) = 2^3 * T(N/2^3) + 3 * N \quad \text{for } i = 3$$

·
·
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$$T(N) = 2^k * T(N/2^k) + k * N \quad \text{for } i = k$$

The algorithm reaches the **base case** when:

$$T(N/2^k) = T(1)$$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

$$T(N) = 2 * T(N/2) + N \quad \text{for } i = 1$$

$$T(N) = 2^2 * T(N/2^2) + 2 * N \quad \text{for } i = 2$$

$$T(N) = 2^3 * T(N/2^3) + 3 * N \quad \text{for } i = 3$$

·
·
·

$$T(N) = 2^k * T(N/2^k) + k * N \quad \text{for } i = k$$

The algorithm reaches the **base case** when:

$$T(N/2^k) = T(1)$$

Hence, $N = 2^k$ and
 $k = \log n$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

$$T(N) = 2 * T(N/2) + N \quad \text{for } i = 1$$

$$T(N) = 2^2 * T(N/2^2) + 2 * N \quad \text{for } i = 2$$

$$T(N) = 2^3 * T(N/2^3) + 3 * N \quad \text{for } i = 3$$

·
·
·

$$T(N) = 2^k * T(N/2^k) + k * N \quad \text{for } i = k$$

Substitute $k = \log N$
into the equation

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

$$T(N) = 2^k * T(N/2^k) + k * N$$

Substitute $k = \log N$ into the equation above:

$$T(N) = N + N * \log N$$

Hence, big-O time complexity of divide and conquer algorithm for maximum contiguous subsequence sum problem is $O(N \log N)$

Kahoot Question #3

Answer the following question:

Skip

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When an algorithm divides a problem into 2 equal halves and solves these halves recursively with $O(N)$ overhead for each half, then what is the big-O complexity of this recursive algorithm?

Answer:
 $O(N \log N)$

▲ $O(\log N)$

◆ $O(N)$

● $O(N \log N)$

■ $O(N^2)$

Master Theorem:

Given the following parameters:

- A , which is the **number of subproblems** in the problem to be solved by divide and conquer technique
- B , **relative size of the subproblems** (for instance $B = 2$ represents half-sized subproblems)
- k , which is the representative of the fact that **overhead is** $\Theta(N^k)$

The solution to the equation $T(N) = AT(N/B) + O(N^k)$, where $A > 1$ and $B > 1$ is:

- $T(N) = O(N^{\log_B A})$, for $A > B^k$
- $T(N) = O(N^k \log N)$, for $A = B^k$
- $T(N) = O(N^k)$, for $A < B^k$

Complexity Analysis: The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

- Let's apply **Master's Theorem** to the time it takes to execute for the **divide and conquer algorithm** for **maximum contiguous subsequence problem**:
- $T(N) = 2T\left(\frac{N}{2}\right) + O(N)$
- General Formula: $T(N) = AT(N/B) + O(N^k)$
- $A = B = 2$ satisfies second condition for $k = 1$ (i.e., $T(N) = O(N^k \log N)$, for $A = B^k$)
- Therefore, $T(N) = O(N \log N)$

The Maximum Contiguous Subsequence Sum Problem

Brute Force Algorithm (i. e., $O(N^3)$ Algorithm)

```
public static int maxContiguousSum(int [] array){
    int maxSum = 0;
    for(int i = 0; i < array.length; i++) {
        for(int j = i; j < array.length; j++) {
            int thisSum = 0;
            for (int k = i; k <= j; k++)
                thisSum += array[k];
            if(thisSum > maxSum)
                maxSum = thisSum; }
        }
    return maxSum;
}
```

Lecture#4

Improved Algorithm (i. e., $O(N^2)$ Algorithm)

- Let's use the fact that $\sum_{k=i}^j A_k = A_j + \sum_{k=i}^{j-1} A_k$

```
public static int maxContiguousSum(int [] array){
    int maxSum = 0;
    for(int i = 0; i < array.length; i++) {
        int thisSum = 0;
        for(int j = i; j < array.length; j++)
        {
            thisSum += array[j];
            if(thisSum > maxSum)
                maxSum = thisSum; }
        }
    return maxSum;
}
```

Lecture#4

Divide and Conquer Algorithm ($O(N \log N)$ complexity)

```
4* public static int maxSumRec(int [] a, int left, int right){
5     int maxLeftBorderSum = 0, maxRightBorderSum = 0;
6     int leftBorderSum = 0, rightBorderSum = 0;
7     int center = (left + right)/2;
8
9     if(left == right) //Base Case
10        return a[left] > 0 ? a[left] : 0;
11
12    int maxLeftSum = maxSumRec(a, left, center);
13    int maxRightSum = maxSumRec(a, center + 1, right);
14
15    for (int i = center; i >= left; i--) {
16        leftBorderSum += a[i];
17        if(leftBorderSum > maxLeftBorderSum)
18            maxLeftBorderSum = leftBorderSum;
19    }
20
21    for (int i = center+1; i <= right; i++) {
22        rightBorderSum += a[i];
23        if(rightBorderSum > maxRightBorderSum)
24            maxRightBorderSum = rightBorderSum;
25    }
26
27    return Math.max(maxLeftSum, Math.max(maxRightSum, (maxLeftBorderSum + maxRightBorderSum)));
28 }
```

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Linear Algorithm (i. e., $O(N)$ Algorithm)

```
public static int maxContiguousSum(int [] array){
    int maxSum = 0;
    int prev = array[0];
    for(int i = 1; i < array.length; i++) {
        if(prev <= 0)
            prev = array[i];
        else
            prev += array[i];
        maxSum = Math.max(prev, maxSum); }
    return maxSum;
}
```

Lecture#4

Kahoot Question #2

Answer the following question:

Skip

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What is the big-O time complexity of the most efficient algorithmic solution for "maximum contiguous subsequence problem"?

Answer: $O(N)$

▲ $O(N \log N)$

◆ $O(N)$

● $O(N^3)$

■ $O(N^2)$

Now, time for In-Class Exercises!!!

